

JURIDICAL SCIENCES

THE CONCEPT OF A GUILTY VERDICT IN CRIMINAL PROCEEDINGS

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Abstract

In a criminal process, for the issuance of any guilty verdict, including a verdict with the imposition of a sentence and release from serving it or without imposing a sentence with release from criminal liability, indisputable proof is required, first of all, of those facts that constitute the content of the accusation resolved by the court. As long as the actual and legal signs of the deed are not established in full accordance with objective reality, the court is not entitled to pass a guilty verdict on the case.

Keywords: criminal process, circumstances, democratic justice, justified sentence, individual case, verdicts, the courts.

Of course, in each individual case, the court carefully examines all other circumstances that are included in the subject of proof in the case and are essential for issuing a lawful and justified sentence. The completeness and comprehensiveness of the study of the case under consideration is one of the main requirements for the administration of democratic justice.

Probable knowledge about any circumstances, the probability of facts are always unresolved doubts about these circumstances or facts. If doubts are eliminated, then the fact or circumstance is considered to be established reliably; it is no longer probable, but certain knowledge¹.

When pronouncing guilty verdicts, the courts must strictly observe the principle of individualization of punishment, as well as take into account the nature and degree of social danger of the crime committed, the identity of the perpetrator and the circumstances mitigating and aggravating responsibility².

Failure to comply with this most important requirement calls into question the justice of the sentence and entails its cancellation.

Similarly, during the judicial investigation, as necessary, the circumstances that were associated with various investigative versions rejected during the criminal prosecution are also examined. In this regard, it is difficult to agree with the statement of M. Grodzinsky that "all the evidence that established the incorrectness of a number of initial versions and, moreover, are not connected with the remaining version, which was recognized as correct, has already played its role in the case and, therefore, will not be considered in the future when the case is resolved by the court at the stage of trial"³. Such a view leads to an unjustified narrowing of the subject and limits of proof in a court session and, in some cases, may adversely affect the interests of establishing objective truth in a case.

Correctly emphasizes A. Starchenko the fact that "the inner conviction of the judges is formed in the process of careful consideration in the court session of all the evidence collected in the case. The role of evidence in the case is performed not only by the facts substantiating ... the accusation, but also by all the circumstances with the help of which the false versions were refuted. If the court is deprived of the opportunity to consider the latter, then thereby it will not have grounds for concluding that this event could not have been caused by other reasons⁴.

But both groups of the mentioned circumstances are investigated by the participants in the trial precisely in connection with the charge brought against the defendant in a specific criminal case. All these circumstances are necessary, first of all, to establish the proof or lack of proof of the accusation resolved by the court. If, under the given circumstances, there is not reliable, but only probable knowledge, a guilty verdict is unacceptable⁵. By themselves, they never provide sufficient grounds for a court to issue a guilty verdict, if the judicial investigation does not establish those specific illegal actions or omissions that are charged to the defendant as containing a certain *corpus delicti*.

In criminal proceedings, the basis for any guilty verdict is the recognition by the court as proven of the charge (in its original form or with possible changes), on which the person has been sent to the court. This conclusion is confirmed by the indication of the criminal procedure law (part (1) of article 389 of the Code of Criminal Procedure) that a judgment of conviction by a court is allowed "only if, as a result of a judicial investigation, the guilt of the defendant in committing a crime is confirmed on the basis of a combination of evidence examined in the court".

Consequently, in order to pass a guilty verdict, it is always necessary to establish, first of all, those facts

¹ I. Ovsyanikov, A. Galkin. Probable and reliable in the guilty verdict // Russian Justice, No. 9, 2000, p.41.

² Decision of the Plenum of the Supreme Court of Justice of the Republic of Moldova „Regarding court sentence” no. 5 of 19.06.2006, p. 35.

³ M. Grodzinsky. Evidence in the Soviet criminal process. "State prosecutor in the Soviet court", M., 1954, p. 64-65.

⁴ A. Starchenko. Logic in forensic research. M., 1958, p. 209-210.

⁵ I. Ovsyanikov, A. Galkin. Probable and reliable in the guilty verdict // Russian Justice, No. 9, 2000, p.41.

that make up the actual plot of the accusation considered by the court in the material and legal sense. Until all these facts are carefully examined, there can be no question of finding the defendant guilty and condemning him as a criminal.

The range of facts that make up the content of each accusation separately is not considered in detail in this work. However, it seems necessary to pay attention to the following significant circumstances.

At the judicial investigation, first of all, the criminal act or omission itself, which is incriminated to the defendant, should be established. The criminal procedural law does not allow a person to be convicted for "objectionable thoughts" or "a dangerous state of mind", it requires for each case to accurately decide "whether there was an act of which the defendant is accused" (paragraph 1) part (1) of Art. 385 Code of Criminal Procedure of the Republic of Moldova).

The principle - the criminal law is the subject of legal regulation, in the context of criminal liability, only certain harmful actions⁶ or inactions, in which the "evil will" of a person has found its concrete expression - underlies the definition of a crime and all institutions of criminal law.

Legal regulation of social relations in general and the imposition of legal responsibility on certain persons is possible only in relation to their specific actions that acquire legal significance.

When resolving charges in court, there are most often gaps associated with the study of the subjective side of the *corpus delicti* seen in the actions or inaction of the defendant.

In order to issue a lawful and justified guilty verdict, the court must, in each criminal case, establish the circumstances of the crime committed in strict accordance with reality and give these circumstances a correct legal assessment, i.e. must establish the objective truth in the criminal case under consideration⁷. As a result of the study, the judges come to knowledge, evidence-based, covering the range of questions, the answers to which should give a guilty verdict.

Sometimes specific facts that characterize the forms of guilt of a criminally responsible person remain unclear, and this inevitably leads either to objective imputation in the absence of any guilt or to an erroneous definition of legal signs and the degree of danger (severity) of the deed.

In order to justify insufficient attention to the study of specific forms of guilt, the investigators sometimes refer to the opinion that the will manifested during the commission of a criminal act is reduced to a purely mental process and its establishment in accordance with objective reality is not always possible.

In criminal law theory, indeed, an opinion is expressed that gives rise to such statements. E. Edelhaus, for example, points out that "volitional action should ... be considered only as a process of thinking that chooses

an act"⁸. However, this point of view cannot be considered valid. The human will is not reduced to a purely mental process, it is objectified from the outside. The will finds its external, objective expression in the concrete actions of a person.

Speaking about the need for a full and comprehensive examination by the court of those facts of the accusation that characterize the subjective side of the *corpus delicti*, one cannot help but focus on the question of the motive and purpose of the defendant committing the action or inaction incriminated to him.

It is known that the motive and purpose, reflected in the consciousness of the actor, induce him to either perform certain actions or refrain from them. The motive is an indispensable element of the will, since without it is difficult to imagine human activity.

The motive always indicates the reason for the commission of the act, and the purpose determines its direction - the immediate result that the actor strives for. Finding out the motive and purpose of the deed not only makes it possible to understand the mental state of a person at the time of the commission of actions or inactions, but also helps to identify the causes of unlawful behavior, determine the form of guilt and the degree of danger of the perpetrator.

Other facts and circumstances that are part of the actual plot of the accusation or necessary for the correct resolution of the question of the guilt of the defendant in the incriminated act and the measures of his responsibility must also be carefully investigated.

At the court session, it is required to establish all these facts and their signs, which have criminal legal significance, in strict accordance with objective reality. Only if recognized by the court reliable evidence constituting the content of the charge brought against the defendant and forming a specific *corpus delicti*, it is permissible to issue a judgment of conviction in the case.

The decision of the Plenum of the Supreme Court of Justice of the Republic of Moldova strictly emphasizes that a guilty verdict cannot be based on assumptions, either exclusively or mainly on the testimony of witnesses obtained during the criminal prosecution and read out in court in their absence⁹.

This provision is universally recognized in the theory of criminal procedure and is consistently carried out in judicial practice. Therefore, we do not share the views of some scientists that the task of establishing the true result of knowledge in each criminal case is obviously not feasible in certain cases.

So, according to the design of S. Kurylev, supported by V. Zablotsky, from the composition of the so-called "main fact" (subject of proof), the central one is singled out - the commission by a person brought to criminal responsibility of a harmful, unlawful, guilty act, which must be proven reliably, and the judgment of

⁶ A. Borodac, M. Gherman. Criminal liability // Law and Life, no. 11, 2005, p. 4.

⁷ V. Zazhitsky. Truth and the means of establishing it in the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Russian Federation: theoretical and legal analysis // State and Law, 2005, No. 6, p. 67-74.

⁸ E. Edelhaus. To the question of the concept of freedom in criminal law // Jurisprudence, 1962, No. 4, p. 140.

⁹ Decision of the Plenum of the Supreme Court of Justice of the Republic of Moldova „Regarding court sentence” no. 5 of 19.06.2006, p. 7.

the court must be true (“absolutely true”), the same elements of the offense as the subjective (forms of intent) and objective sides of the crime, as well as other circumstances of the crime committed, can be established on the basis of assumptions¹⁰.

Analyzing these views in detail, M. Strogovich came to the only correct conclusion that “a guilty verdict can only be established on facts that have been proven with certainty, and it cannot be based on probable facts, no matter how high their degree of probability”¹¹.

According to S. Kurylev, the court, if it could not establish whether the defendant committed robbery or theft, finds him guilty of theft¹². Therefore, this conclusion of the judges is based on conjecture. However, during a robbery, a person is aware that his actions are being observed by other persons and ignores this circumstance, therefore, if it is established in court that this awareness is absent, then such a sign of theft as “secret kidnapping” has been reliably proven.

To pass a guilty verdict, the court must have a sufficient body of evidence confirming the correctness of the solution of all issues to be resolved in this judicial act, because the prosecution, as E. Mizulina, this is an activity carried out by the persons specified in the law, to justify the guilt of the defendant before the court¹³.

Summarizing, it seems possible to propose the following concept of a guilty verdict in a criminal process: a guilty verdict is the most important act of justice pronounced in the name of the law by the court of first instance on the guilt of the defendant and on the application or non-application of punishment to him, as well as on all others related to the end of legal proceedings, questions.

References

1. A. Borodac, M. Gherman. Criminal liability // Law and Life, no. 11, 2005, p. 4.
2. A. Starchenko. Logic in forensic research. M., 1958, p. 209-210.
3. Decision of the Plenum of the Supreme Court of Justice of the Republic of Moldova „Regarding court sentence” no. 5 of 19.06.2006, p. 35.
4. Decision of the Plenum of the Supreme Court of Justice of the Republic of Moldova „Regarding court sentence” no. 5 of 19.06.2006, p. 7.
5. E. Edelhauz. To the question of the concept of freedom in criminal law // Jurisprudence, 1962, No. 4, p. 140.
6. E. Mizulina. Criminal procedure: the concept of state self-restraint. Tartu, 1991, p. 4.
7. I. Ovsyanikov, A. Galkin. Probable and reliable in the guilty verdict//Russian Justice, No. 9,2000, p.41.
8. I. Ovsyanikov, A. Galkin. Probable and reliable in the guilty verdict // Russian Justice, No. 9, 2000, p.41.
9. M. Grodzinsky. Evidence in the Soviet criminal process. "State prosecutor in the Soviet court", M., 1954, p. 64-65.
10. M. Strogovich. The truth of the judgment. - M., 1974, p. 52.
11. S. Kurylev. On reliability and probability in justice // Jurisprudence, No. 1, 1968.
12. V. Zablotsky. On the relationship between the requirements of the validity and truth of a guilty verdict with the rule on the interpretation of doubts in favor of the defendant. - “Proceedings of Irkutsk. Univ., vol. 85, legal series, no. X, part 4, 1970.
13. V. Zazhitsky. Truth and the means of establishing it in the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Russian Federation: theoretical and legal analysis // State and Law, 2005, No. 6, p. 67-74.

¹⁰ S. Kurylev. On reliability and probability in justice //Jurisprudence, 1968, No. 1; see also: V. Zablotsky. On the relationship between the requirements of the validity and truth of a guilty verdict with the rule on the interpretation of doubts in favor of the defendant. - “Proceedings of Irkutsk. Univ., vol. 85, legal series, no. X, part 4, 1970.

¹¹ M. Strogovich. The truth of the judgment. - M., 1974, p. 52.

¹² S. Kurylev. On reliability and probability in justice // Jurisprudence, No. 1, 1968.

¹³ E. Mizulina. Criminal procedure: the concept of state self-restraint. Tartu, 1991, p. 4.